

Women Empowerment through SHG for Sustainable Future

Dr Asha Singh
The Glocal University
Commerce and Business
Email-ashanikitha@gmail.com

Abstract

Many believe that microfinance, which operates on a group basis, can significantly help the poor by enhancing their access to capital. When Dr. Muhammad Yunus established Grameena Bank in 1976 in Bangladesh, Dr. Muhammad Yunus was a trailblazer in the field of microcredit. A pilot initiative for bank connection with self-help groups was launched by NABARD in 1992. Self-Help Groups (SHGs) are cooperative organizations whose members voluntarily bring together people from similar socioeconomic situations. In rural areas, The poor's economic and social development, as well as women's empowerment, are greatly aided by SHGs. This study looks at how self-help groups (SHGs) have transformed the socioeconomic status of rural Indian women and how they have helped the UN achieve its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). We explicitly addressed SDGs including no poverty (SDG 1), zero hunger (SDG 2), good health and well-being (SDG 3), high-quality education (SDG 4), and gender equality (SDG 5) in order to examine the impact of SHGs on rural women in this study. Everyone can see that the SHG bank connection program is sustainable and viable because of the funding of SHGs. To sum up, the most effective method and tool for alleviating poverty and empowering women is microfinance through SHGs. The SHG program's microfinance initiatives have improved the mental health and social empowerment of rural women. When calculating a composite index of women's empowerment, just three criteria are considered: economic empowerment, autonomy, and gender relations.

Keywords: SHG, Empowerment, Gender Equality, SDG , Sustainability, Poverty Reduction, Microfinance.

INTRODUCTION

In the introduction section we will be discussing the works related to themes of the study, basically Women empowerment, SHGs, the results from SHG membership and SDGs. India is still one of the world's developing nations. However, this was called the Golden Bird a couple of centuries ago. There was an abundance of beautiful scenery, intelligent people, agricultural products, minerals, and nature. India had the highest per capita income before the British invasion. The population remained stable, and there was an abundance of food for everyone. Trade with other countries and the agricultural sector were both booming. From religious observance and intellectual achievement to monetary prosperity, we were unrivaled. India was almost as large as Europe in the 1500s, accounting for 24.5% of world trade. As a whole, the world was still relying on barter when the Greeks and Indians started using money. India used to be a lot more forward-thinking when it came to gender equality. It is true that female deities are venerated in Indian mythology. Women in that era were fierce, self-reliant, and unafraid.

Countless nations have exercised control and occupation over India. As a result of its recent spate of setbacks, the nation's prestige has been dwindling, and it is currently lagging behind in all areas. Aiming to become known as Sone ki Chidiya by 2022, India aspires to be proclaimed by Prime Minister Narendra Modi. However, this can only be achieved by nurturing the core elements of the family, which encompass women.

The concept of self-help groups was one that empowered women. Some point to NABARD's initial heavy promotion of SHGs in 1991 and 1992 as the start of the SHG movement.

It wasn't until 1993 that SHGs were granted more banking privileges by the Reserve Bank of India. The trend has been expedited by the availability of financial services. For organizations that help women help themselves to survive in the long run, government-backed bank loans are a lifesaver. Obtaining low-interest loans is one method that women's self-help groups can empower themselves with. Members can borrow money from the organization with low interest and no collateral for unexpected expenses by contributing to a common fund on a monthly basis (Singh, 2008). Locally, Self-Help Groups (SHGs) provide low-income individuals—particularly women—with the tools they need to find work, hone their skills, increase their income, and escape poverty (Duncombe and Heeks, 2002; Deininger and Liu, 2009). According to Duncombe and Heeks (2002), micro and small business owners can find a home in a strong SHG fraternity. This, in turn, gives these entrepreneurs more leeway with their money and helps low-income women put more of their resources into local businesses rather than spending it on consumption. Promoting women's economic independence is central to self-help groups. Despite the pervasiveness of sustainable development problems, it is not always easy to incorporate them into public policy. But if we provide women the tools they need to become self-sufficient, we can ensure our success in the long run. According to the Brundtland report, the consensus definition of sustainable development is to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Proposals for sustainable growth were put out. As stated in their 1980 report *The World Conservation Strategy*, the IUCN stressed the importance of considering social and economic aspects in addition to ecological ones in order for development to be deemed sustainable.

The main idea of Self-Help Groups is to provide empowerment to women and give them strength to face problems. These groups entitle them to raise revenue, improve living style &

condition in the community (Gupta & Aggarwal, 2015). It tries to pull up backward people of the society and meet them with the community. Finally, the country dissects the benefits of socialism.

To pull up the villagers, different kinds of plans have been launched through the Government of India and state governments. Nevertheless, rural poverty and unemployment conditions did not vary very much day by day. It became rigid and intense but our government took the initiative to overcome poverty. The data of the Indian Economy shows the bitter result as approx. 27% of the population lives below the poverty line.

In the Indian Economy, containing a huge part of the population, it performs a significant role in household activities as well as national activities (Sundaram, 2012). It contains approx. 1/3 part of the labor force of the nation. Female participants give a big part of their income for conservation which shows that amount earned by women directly & undoubtedly impresses the phenomenon & conservation of indigence.

Self Help Groups work on associative theory & give a marketplace for participants to develop support for each other. This is mainly recognized as a means of strengthening the process. These clusters are mainly built for poor people who are not approaching banking institutions in the consolidated portion. Deficiency in reliability & transparency is causing a severe problem in the cluster. In spite of this, Self Help Groups are insured through the blanket activity of the fellow. This plan was mainly organized for villagers, particularly women, to constitute a cluster for fraternal advantages.

In light of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the UN, namely no poverty (SDG 1), zero hunger (SDG 2), good health and well-being (SDG 3), high-quality education (SDG 4), and gender equality (SDG 5), this study looks at the effect of SHGs on the socioeconomic development of rural women in India. In order to set the stage for this conversation, the study begins by critically evaluating the recent literature on the SDGs in relation to SHGs. This is followed by an examination of how rural women's involvement in SHGs helps to achieve SDGs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 goals. In this sense, SHGs' facilitation of the socioeconomic growth of rural women depends heavily on their ability to obtain microcredit. The importance of microcredit in accomplishing the Sustainable Development Goals has drawn scholarly attention to the study of

the effects of SHGs on women's socio economic development. In light of this, the study intends to investigate two important questions: first, whether or not rural women's involvement in SHGs might affect their socioeconomic growth; and second, whether or not rural women's awareness levels can fluctuate both before and after SHG participation.

OBJECTIVES OF SELF HELP GROUPS (SHGS)

- 1.The Self-Help Groups are businesses. For daily necessities, little sums of money are raised. When the saving groups are converted to earning groups, women's output and credibility are both increased.
- 2.Women have several opportunities to learn about banking, gram panchayats, zilla parishads, law, and the judiciary, among other topics.
3. The family structure is preserved as long as affordable alternatives are available.
- 4.SHGs are a useful tool for putting an end to consumer exploitation.
- 5.The growth of self-assurance is attained.
- 6.There is a shared forum for discussion and idea exchange.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The emphasis in the field of sustainable development for women living in rural areas needs to be on empowering women by giving them more influence in the economy, society, participation, and decision-making processes.To a great extent, this is made possible by the creation of SHGs. Economic, social, and cultural sustainability make up the three pillars of sustainable development. The primary goal of SHGs is economic sustainability. This essay reviews the body of research on the role of self-help groups to sustainable development. The emphasis in the field of sustainable development for women living in rural areas needs to be on empowering women

by giving them more influence in the economy, society, participation, and decision-making. To a great extent, this is made possible by the creation of SHGs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To comprehend the contribution that self-help groups provide to sustainable development.
2. To examine the income-generating activities that SHGs are promoting.
3. The primary aim of this study is to examine the empowerment of women through self-help groups. The specific goal is to ascertain how SHG members' economic circumstances have changed.

REVIEW LITERATURE

Extensive studies by many researchers in different countries have focused on the theoretical and empirical aspects of self-help groups. Further, they have highlighted the link between self-help groups and improving the socio-economic status of rural women.

SHGs aim to promote sustainable socio-economic development, discuss their problems, and resolve them through exact decision making ways by decision making participation process. (Balraj and Rao, 2016) called these local organizations with its objectives. So SHGs work as Quasi-banks, using the members' savings and loans from the banks to lend their members.

Richa Made a study in the Meerut district to see the impact of SHGs in upliftment of the poor and the case study was done on female SHGs. She studied 300 women from female SHGs and 300 men from male SHGs in Meerut District and Used Qualitative and Quantitative-with Survey Method and Depth Interview". The research was specified to study the components affecting

micro financing, the impact of microfinance in women empowerment, to study whether the economically benefited what proportion of, expenditure and how much is savings of the members after joining self-help Groups. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of self-help groups on employment, poverty reduction, and gender equality in Meerut by comparing the effectiveness of women's and men's SHGs.

Qualitative and quantitative-a questionnaire was used to collect a total of 811 sample respondents, out of which 210 respondents from Dakshina Kannada, 216 respondents from Udupi, 198 respondents from Devanagari and 187 respondents from Haveri were selected as samples for the case-study. The objective was to understand the need to empower women, examine the social and economic profiles of the respondents as members of SHGs, understand the nature, functioning, programmes and problems of SHGs and SHG members., so that SHGs can be assessed. Contribute to empower rural women so that they can achieve socio-economic independence and mobility - to understand how SHGs instill confidence in women to achieve 'gender equality' In patriarchal male dominated gender biased male dominated societies ensure their individual place in family and social life (Singh et al., 2020).

There were many studies which were going on in that era on the topic of discussion but the most important study concerned women's strengths and potency, noting that the phrase or idea of empowerment did not originate in a gender context, but was invented by Brazilian educator Paulo Freire (1921-1997). Along with this, the role of NGOs was also explained here. Also, it is behind China and Bangladesh. At 17 per cent, women's contribution to India's GDP was lower than the global average of 37 per cent. After India's Independence, the Government's main focused field was developing, formulating and creating new policies for Empowering Women's and There were policies introduced that time which give full power to Females in Developing

and empowering them (Mohan, 2016). He also focused on the roles of Government and NGOs as they have prioritized women's economic contributions through self-employment and industrial companies.

We can see that gradually with the “improvement in the lives of women” they had started becoming less reliable on the males for their life and financial support. With all the growth of the particular trading class inside society during previous centuries, women began learning basic enterprise skills and attained elegant entrepreneurship information to start-up their own particular businesses. MFIs were the one which provided both financial and non-financial help to the poor people (Dondo, 1991). His works covered the complications he faced in India and also provided us with research on Women and Development (Seth, 2001).

set out to investigate the challenges and possibilities encountered by female entrepreneurs in India and

Prakash and Goyan Proven that female entrepreneurs are determined, hardworking, and competitive; so, there needs to be an ongoing endeavor to motivate, educate, and assess women's entrepreneurship on an individual and corporate level (Goyal and Parkash, 2011).

Singh, examined the reasons behind women's entrepreneurship, the ways in which they built their companies, the difficulties and barriers they encountered in their attempts. Major barriers to the emergence of women entrepreneurs have been identified, including gender discrimination, family obligations, social rejection of female entrepreneurs and a dearth of interaction with prosperous business owners (Singh, 2018).

Over 1.5 million women in one of Northern India's poorest rural regions have joined a self-help group initiative. That application is examined in this work. The four main principles of the program are microsavings, education on nutrition and health, training for agricultural

entrepreneurs, and political engagement. How participating in a program can enhance one's standard of living is the focus of this study. The research estimates propensity score matching models and exhibits evidence of variances in specific dimensions using fresh data on a range of self-reported capability indicators from members and non-members. It also draws attention to the substantial advantages enjoyed by the most marginalized members of society, the scheduled castes and tribes. After examining robustness, Anand, Saxena, Gonzalez, and Dang's (2019) research demonstrated that the program made a contribution to some areas of sustainable development.

Every nation is built on a foundation of education and research centered on sustainable growth. Policies for sustainable development also place a strong emphasis on education, which is now necessary to increase environmental protection knowledge among researchers, teachers, students, and local populations. An overview of how research and higher education support a country's sustainable growth is given in the current article. A summary of the state of the country's financial institutions, both state and federal, and the higher education system has also been attempted (Sharma, 2014).

Self-Help Groups for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

There is an increasing amount of research on how SHGs contribute to women's self-reliance, as microcredit through SHGs plays a major role in contributing to achieving the SDGs. Several SDGs are directly or indirectly affected by the availability of microcredit through self-help groups. A few possible applications and functions that SHGs might have in accomplishing SDGs are shown in Figure 1. There have been extensive discussions in the literature regarding the possible direct impact of SHGs on accomplishing SDG 1.

Individuals who earn 2 USD or 3 USD per day and are economically disadvantaged can apply for microcredit through SHGs. (Murugesan and Ganapathi, 2010; Wickramasinghe and Fernando, 2017) Low-income households may benefit from this system by having better financial circumstances and being able to sustain a consistent level of consumption. Another grave problem that affects people everywhere is malnutrition. (Adamsen and Rasmussen, 2001) Many researchers have looked into the relationship between participants' nutritional status and SHG program participation in an effort to discover a solution to this problem. According to research by (Hamad and Fernald, 2015), employing microcredit through SHGs had a positive effect on participants' levels of food security and nutritional status.

Individuals with low socioeconomic position and those living in poverty typically have poor health. By giving low-income people the financial means, microcredit through SHGs enables them to start small businesses, increase income, and get closer to economic independence. (Deaton, 2008) Consequently, the consensus across the globe is that wealth and health are related. (Mahajan, 2005) Poverty and health disparities are inextricably linked, and microcredit via Self-Help Groups (SHGs) programs provides ways to address multiple of these problems at once. (Brody et al.,2015), low-income families that take part in SHGs programs have a higher chance of being able to obtain insurance. In addition, the utilization of microcredit through SHG initiatives can help facilitate the fulfillment of SDG 4.

In order to maintain their current quality of life, many low-income rural families employ their children to work on family farms, which makes up the bulk of these households. Children continue to skip school as a direct result. With the help of microcredit from SHGs, these families may stabilize their financial status and increase the likelihood that their kids will attend school. (Nader, 2008) Nader found a strong link between children's education and microcredit obtained through SHGs. Based on the discussion, we discovered that the introduction of microcredit through SHGs has raised household consumption, empowered people to access better health care, improved the nutritional supply for children, transformed the income levels of rural women, and encouraged women's empowerment. It has also increased savings to help achieve SDGs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Fig.1 Shows the Framework of SHGs to Achieve SDGs

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Exploratory study that draws off earlier reviews of the literature.

Sources of Data: Secondary sources, such as websites, journals, books, and published research, are a major source of data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The emphasis in the field of sustainable development for women living in rural areas needs to be on empowering women by giving them more influence in the economy, society, participation, and decision-making. To a great extent, this is made possible by the creation of SHGs.

For rural and migrant populations, Self-Help Groups (SHGs) have given them a stable means of subsistence, enabling them to grow without external pressure and with full effort. Sustainability is understood in terms of the financial, economic, and social spheres, where people actively contribute to the growth of businesses, families, and cultures. It is evident from the discussion above that SHGs are a means of empowering women and achieving sustainable livelihoods in both urban and Indian villages.

Figure 1- Sustainable Employment via SHG

RECOMMENDATIONS

SHGs should receive sufficient financial help from the government in the form of concessions. To ensure that the members of SHGs are qualified, the government should arrange for the appropriate occupational training. To ensure that SHGs are operating efficiently, the district authority might have to implement a day-to-day system. The government ought to take the required actions to enable and motivate all impoverished rural women to join SHGs.

Regulatory bodies are taking the creation and promotion of SHGs seriously, as evidenced by new guidelines and policy frameworks. In addition, the government has promised funding for this industry in an effort to alleviate financial difficulties, indicating that there will be more opportunities for new businesses to emerge in the future. In order to verify transparency and establish a single portal for quick entry into this industry, this will be useful for audit and research purposes.

CONCLUSION

It has been discovered that microfinance via SHGs is the best strategy and practical instrument for reducing poverty and empowering rural women. The SHGs have revolutionized the lives of rural women by empowering them to become independent, self-sufficient, and self-employed. It is concluded from study that it is a gradual and consistent procedure and women have started taking additional responsibilities and they are willing to become fully developed in all ways for the family and Living. The concept of SHGs has not only motivated the Rural Women but also the Semi Urban Women population for the improvement of their living conditions. It is also concluded that SHGs is a path to abolish poverty in India through women empowerment.

The results also emphasized the significance of SHGs in accomplishing SDGs. In addition to enhancing the lives of individual women, the financial and social empowerment of rural women—facilitated by Self-Help Groups—contributes to the overall growth of the community and the country. Consequently, the study's findings unambiguously demonstrated that enabling rural women through SHG microcredit is a critical step towards the realization of a developed, just, and inclusive society. The findings highlighted the necessity of expanding and maintaining

these kinds of programs in order to guarantee long-term socioeconomic growth and the accomplishment of the SDGs in India's rural areas. However, the study's cross-sectional methodology restricts causal inference, its dependence on source data from SHG members may introduce bias, and its district-specific focus may have an impact on the conclusions' application.

REFERENCES

Balraj, I., & Rao, R.S.B. (2016). RESEARCH ARTICLE IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY OF SHGs. *International Journal of Research in Management, Science and Technology*, Issue 8-16

Sharma .R (2009) Sustainable development : The way for the future, where are you?. *Indian Journal of community medicine*. 34 (4). 276-278

Murugesan, J., Ganapathi, R., 2010. Impact of microfinance on the economic status of members of the self-help groups. *Asia Pac. Bus. Rev.* 6(3), 74–87.

Nader, Y.F., 2008. Microcredit and the socio-economic wellbeing of women and their families in Cairo. *J. Socio. Econ.* 37(2), 644–656.

Nayak .AK, Panigrahi P.K and Swain B (2019) Self help groups in India : challenges and a roadmap for sustainability. Vol.16. pp 1013-1033.

Hamad, R., Fernald, L.C., 2015. Microcredit participation and women's health: Results from a cross-sectional study in Peru. *International Journal for Equity in Health*. 14, 1–10.

Adamsen, L., Rasmussen, J.M., 2001. Sociological perspectives on self-help groups: Reflections on conceptualization and social processes. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 35(6), 909–917.

Deaton, A., 2008. Income, health, and well-being around the world: Evidence from the Gallup World Poll. *J. Econ. Perspect.* 22(2), 53–72.

Mahajan, V., 2005. From microcredit to livelihood finance. *Econ. Polit. Wkly.* 40(41), 4416–4419.

Brody, C., De Hoop, T., Vojtkova, M., et al., 2015. Economic self-help group programs for improving women's empowerment: A systematic review. *Campbell Syst. Rev.* 11(1), doi: 10.4073/csr.2015.19

Sharma .R (2014) Sustainable development : The way for the future, where are you?. *Indian Journal of community medicine.* 34 (4). 276-278

Gupta, M. S., & Aggarwal, M. A. (2015). Opportunities and Challenges faced by Women Entrepreneurs in India. *17(8)*, 69–73. doi.org/10.9790/487X-17836973

Deininger, K., & Liu, Y. (2009). Longer-Term Economic Impacts of Self-Help Groups in India. (March). Retrieved from pdfs.semanticscholar.org/43c8/73907f0ae4467a338c476359c3d00a7ab797.pdf

Sundaram, A. (2012). Impact of Self-help Groups in Socio-economic development of India. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(1), 20–27. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/f27e/e7d81e6bb4c88582ebd28665e31ca5b8b70b.pdf>

Singh, S., Prakash, C., & Ramakrishna, S. (2020, August). Three-dimensional printing in the fight against novel virus COVID-19: Technology helping society during an infectious disease pandemic. *Technology in Society*, 62, 101305.

Mohan, L. (2016). Women Empowerment in India : Issues and Challenges. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 21(10), 50–56. doi.org/10.9790/0837-2110045056

Aleke-Dondo, C. (1991). Survey and analysis of credit programmes for Small and Micro enterprises in Kenya. Kenya Rural Enterprise Programme, K-REP publication research series ; no. 2

Seth, S. (2001). A Critique of Disciplinary Reason: The Limits of Political Theory. *Alternatives: Global, Local, Political*, 26(1), 73–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030437540102600104>